

Urban Preparedness for Emerging Risks in the Baltic Sea Region Data Plan

Version 2

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Urban Preparedness for Emerging Risks in the Baltic Sea Region", No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0051.

Project will evaluate urban preparedness for emerging risks in the Baltic Sea region - specifically focusing on Tallinn, Riga, Vilnius, Helsinki, and Berlin/Hamburg/Munich. Our objective is to examine how political institutions shape preparedness, how city councils implement action plans, the involvement of citizens in this process, and the overall readiness of both institutions and citizens to respond to emerging threats. By bridging the gap between academic disciplines such as preparedness, resilience, communication and state-citizen relations, we aim to provide actionable insights for policymakers tailored to the needs of the urban populations of the Baltic Sea region. The project will proceed in five work packages, resulting in two high-quality academic articles to be published in international peer reviewed academic journals, a set of policy guidelines, and workshops and conferences on the topic.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience
Facility project "Internal and
External Consolidation of the
University of Latvia"
(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Ieva Birka (0000-0002-4453-7825), Didzis Kļaviņš (0000-0002-9096-
6719)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Urban Preparedness for Emerging Risks in the Baltic Sea Region Data Plan](#)

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Urban Preparedness for Emerging Risks in the Baltic Sea Region, (No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0051)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Survey data

Existing data set, collected from the Council of Baltic Sea States project "Prepared Together: Stronger Together" which is a set of 1,000 respondents from each Helsinki, Tallinn, Riga, Vilnius and Munich/Hamburg/Berlin will be used. The existing data will be analyzed in the context of the research project to establish the preparedness level of the urban population.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

New data set from 2025 collected from 1,000 respondents from each Helsinki, Riga, Tallinn, Vilnius, and Munich/Hamburg/Berlin will be used. The data will be analysed in the context of the research project to establish the preparedness level of the urban population.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The project requires annual data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other researchers, as well as the supranational and national government representatives.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

The depository of choice among researchers.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

NotePad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ieva Birka (0000-0002-4453-7825)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Interview data

The project will collect 5 interviews in each of the three countries, in total 15 interviews. The interviews will be recorded and transcribed.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Project requires specific interviews with selected participants.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers.

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2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Requests made to the project leader and access granted on individual basis.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv/en/>

Latvian research data repository and data stewards network. The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for long-term preservation and publication of research data.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

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- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

First, we will follow institutional guidelines for data collection and handling. Making sure we obtain consent for data collection from the interview subjects, and their preference/consent for data sharing.

We do not expect to be working with sensitive data, however, if the subject specifies that he/she would like to remain anonymous, we will take the necessary steps to protect their identity. Then we would limit data access controls to only the involved project participants, we would use storage that enables two-factor authentication (2FA), such as the University of Latvia OneDrive. The data would also be anonymized by removing identifiable information in transcripts and metadata. Store the key file mapping identifiers separately in a secure location.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

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No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

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